

On spider families (Arachnida: Araneae) new to Armenia

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, 11 families (Agelenidae, Filistatidae, Hahniidae, Liocranidae, Mimetidae, Mysmenidae, Oecobiidae, Pholcidae, Phrurolithidae, Sparassidae and Uloboridae), 18 genera and 18 species of spiders new to Armenia are reported. One genus, *Mesiotelus* Simon, 1897 (Liocranidae) is new to the entire Caucasus. Illustrations are provided for six species.

KEYWORDS: Aranei, spiders, Caucasus, Palaearctic, new records.

ԱՄՓՈՓՈՒՄ

Այս հոդվածում ներկայացված են Հայաստանի ֆաունայի համար, սարդերի 11 նոր ընտանիքներ (Agelenidae, Filistatidae, Hahniidae, Liocranidae, Mimetidae, Mysmenidae, Oecobiidae, Pholcidae, Phrurolithidae, Sparassidae և Uloboridae), 18 սեռ և 18 տեսակ: Մեկ սեռ *Mesiotelus* Simon, 1897 (Liocranidae) գրանցված է առաջին անգամ ամբողջ Կովկասի համար: Պատկերները տրվել են վեց տեսակի համար:

ԲԱՆԱԼԻ ԲԱՌԵՐ: Aranei, սարդեր, Կովկաս, Պալեարկտիկ, նոր գրանցումներ:

INTRODUCTION

Armenia is the least studied country in the whole Caucasus and among all former USSR republics as regards the spider diversity (Mikhailov 2021). Currently, only 201 spiders species are reported from Armenia, which is a very low figure in comparison to 615 species known in Georgia and 722 in Azerbaijan (Nentwig *et al.* 2021). Many more species are known in the adjacent Iran (883, Zamani *et al.* 2021) and Turkey (1129, Danişman *et al.* 2021). The situation is the same with the number of families known in the region: 21 in Armenia compared to 54 in Turkey and Iran.

The lack of comprehensive data on the spider fauna of this country is the result of scarce number of local arachnologists and expeditions during the past century. A recent joint Armenian-Russian collecting trip in 2021 revealed that the diversity of spiders in Armenia is much higher than currently known, the results of which are partially reported herein.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The collecting trip was undertaken by three coauthors on May 4–19, 2021. Various collecting methods were used, including sweeping, hand picking, sifting and night collecting. All material was preserved in 96 % ethanol to be later used for molecular analysis, if necessary. The material is temporary stored in the Zoological Museum of the University of Turku.

Photographs were taken using an Olympus SZX16 stereomicroscope with a Canon EOS 7D camera at the Zoological Museum of the University of Turku, and prepared using the Helicon Focus 7.6.2 Pro (<http://www.heliconsoft.com>).

The male and female symbols in brackets refer to subadult specimens. The material is listed in the chronological and alphabetic orders.

References to publications are provided for lesser known species. The full list of taxonomic references can be found in the WSC (2021).

TAXONOMY

Family Agelenidae C.L. Koch, 1837

Although this is a diverse family in the Caucasus with about 35 species in 10 genera (Otto 2020), surprisingly it has not been reported from Armenia until now. We have found at least three genera and species of this family in most sampled localities.

Agelena labyrinthica (Clerck, 1757)

Material examined: *Ararat Province:* 1♂, env. of Lanjar, 39°49'N 44°58'E, 28.v.2021. *Yerevan:* 2 juv., Botanical Garden, 40°12'38"N 44°33'25"E, sweeping and litter, 17.v.2021.

Comments: This species is known from almost 60 localities in the Caucasus (Otto 2020): in the Russian part, as well as in Georgia and Azerbaijan. Juveniles of *A. labyrinthica*, *A. orientalis* (C.L. Koch, 1837) and *Allagelena gracilens* (C.L. Koch, 1841) look similar. However, the juvenile specimens from the Botanical Garden most probably belong to *A. labyrinthica*, which is a transpalearctic species known from Armenia; the specimens have also been collected in the habitat common for this species.

Persiscape gideoni (Levy, 1996)

Agelescape dunini Guseinov, Marusik & Koponen, 2005: 158, figs 1–2, 6–8 (♂ ♀).

Persiscape gideoni: Zamani & Marusik 2020a: 376, figs 3C–D, 6A, I, 9A, 11C–D, 12H–L (♂ ♀).

Material examined: *Ararat Province:* 3 juv., env. of Urtsadzor, 39°54'00"N 44°50'53"E, 1200–1300 m, on clay slope, 6.v.2021; 1 juv., env. of Urtsalanj, 39°49'N 44°59'E, 1800 m, 11.v.2021. *Vayots Dzor Province:* 1(♀), env. of Gnishik, 39°40'18"N 45°17'40"E, ca. 2030 m, 11.v.2021. *Armavir Province:* 3 juv., SW from Yerevan, Jrarbi, 40°04'46"N 44°14'27"E, saline ground and around water ponds, 13.v.2021; 1♂ 2♀ 1 juv., 40°04'59"N 44°11'26"E, collapsing clay cliffs and near water, 13.v.2021. *Kotayk Province:* 1♀ 4 juv., env. of Geghadir, 2 canyons nearby, 40°09'N 44°38'E, 15.v.2021.

Comments: This is the most widespread species of the genus in the region, occurring from Turkey to central Iran (Zamani & Marusik 2020a). Most specimens were collected from the clay-cliff crevices.

Tegenaria domestica (Clerck, 1757)

Material examined: *Ararat Province:* 2♀ 7 juv., Garni Gorge, Azat River, 40°06'32"N 44°43'57"E, 1240 m, 5.v.2021; 1(♀) env. of Goravan, Goravan Sands State Sanctuary, 39°53'51"N 44°43'35"E, 6.v.2021. *Kotayk Province:* 2♀ 7 juv., env. of Geghadir, 2 canyons, 40°09'N 44°38'E, 15.v.2021. *Gegharkunik Province:* 1 juv., Sevan L., env. of Tsovagyugh, 40°37'12"N 44°57'55"E, 1920 m, 8.v.2021. *Vayots Dzor Province:* 2(♂ ♀), Shatin, Scenic place, 39°50'49"N 45°19'00"E, 9.v.2021; 2(♂) 1(♀), env. of Shatin, 39°51'44"N 45°20'19"E, meadow with lava stones, 9.v.2021. *Shirak Province:* 1(♂) 2 juv., foothills of Aragats Mt., 40°23'N 44°13'E, ca. 2200 m, 16.v.2021. *Yerevan:* 2♀, Scientific Centre of Zoology and Hydroecology, garden, 40°12'47"N 44°32'00"E, 1150 m, 1.vi.2021.

Comments: The species is currently known from over 80 records in the Caucasus (Otto 2020). Five adult females in our material are similar to *T. domestica* but may

Fig. 1: General appearance of *Filistata lehtineni*: (A) male, dorsal; (B) female, dorsal; (C) male prosoma, dorsal; (D) female prosoma, dorsal.

belong to other closely related species, and until the collection of corresponding males, their identification remains tentative. Juveniles may also belong to another species.

Family Filistatidae Simon, 1864

The family is represented in the Caucasus by six species in the genera *Filistata* Latreille, 1810, *Pritha* Lehtinen, 1967 and *Zaitunia* Lehtinen, 1967 (Marusik *et al.* 2019). Three species are known in Azerbaijan and three in Georgia (Mikhailov 2021). New to Armenia.

Filistata lehtineni Marusik & Zonstein, 2014

(Figs 1–3)

Filistata lehtineni Zonstein & Marusik, 2019: 74, figs 16A–H, 17A–C, 27B (♂ ♀).

Material examined: *Ararat Province*: 1♀ or juv., Garni Gorge, Azat River, 40°06'32"N 44°43'57"E, 1240 m, 5.v.2021; 7♀ or juv., 2 juv., env. of Urtsadzor, 39°55'26"N 44°48'53"E, 1040 m, clay canyons, 6.v.2021. *Vayot Dzor Province*: 1♂ 2 juv., Gnishik River canyon, road to Noravank Monastery, 39°41'14"N 45°13'21"E, 1400 m, 10.v.2021.

Fig. 2: Male palp of *Filistata lehtineni*: (A) terminal part, retrolateral; (B) cymbium and bulb, anterior; (C) whole palp, retrolateral. Scale = 0.2 mm, if not indicated otherwise.

Fig. 3: Webs of *Filistata lehtineni* made among furrows in the stony cliffs.

Comments: The species was described from Nakhchivan and later reported from the adjacent Iran (Marusik & Zamani 2015). This species well differs from other congeners in the region by the screwed embolus (Fig. 2). We illustrate the habitus (demonstrating the characteristic pattern of both male and female; Fig. 1), the male palp (Fig. 2) and the webs (Fig. 3) made among furrows in the stony cliffs. Bulb of this species has a characteristic slicing that has not been documented before (Fig. 2A, B). Our current material represents the northwesternmost record of the species within its whole known range.

Family Hahniidae Bertkau, 1878

This family is known in the Caucasus by three species belonging to three genera, two species of them known from a single record (Otto 2020). New to Armenia.

Hahnia nava (Blackwall, 1841)

(Fig. 4)

Material examined: *Gegharkunik Province:* 1♂, Sevan Lake, env. of Tsovaguyugh, 40°37'12"N 44°57'55"E, 1920 m, 8.v.2021.

Comments: The single male found in Armenia was collected as a result of sifting pine litter. Earlier it was known from the coast of Black Sea in northern Georgia and Russia (Otto 2020).

Fig. 4: Male of *Hahnia nava*: (A) habitus, dorsal; (B) palp, retrolateral; (C) palp, dorsal-retrolateral; (D) palp, ventral; (E) palp, dorsal. Scale = 0.2 mm, if not indicated otherwise.

Family Liocranidae Simon, 1897

This family is represented by six species in three genera in the Caucasus (Otto 2020), and only recently reported from Armenia on the basis of material identified as *Liocranum rupicola* (Walckenaer, 1830) (Zarikian & Kalashian 2021). Still, this family has not been included in the database of Caucasian spiders (Otto 2020) and in the Mikhailov's (2021) catalog. Among the material collected in Armenia, we found *Mesiotelus*, a genus not mentioned for the Caucasus by Otto (2020) or Mikhailov (2021), although it was reported from the mainland Azerbaijan (Marusik & Guseinov 2003) and Nakhchivan (Marusik *et al.* 2005) as *Mesiotelus* sp.

Agroeca cuprea Menge, 1873

Material examined: *Ararat Province*: 2♀, env. of Urtsadzor, 39°54'00"N 44°50'53"E, 1200–1300 m, on clay slope, 6.v.2021; 1♀, env. of Urtsadzor, 39°55'26"N 44°48'53"E, 1040 m, clay canyons, 6.v.2021. *Vayots Dzor Province*: 1♀, Shatin, Scenic place, 39°50'49"N 45°19'E, 9.v.2021. *Kotayk Province*: 1♀, env. of Solak, 40°28'24"N 44°42'57"E, 14.v.2021.

Comments: Females of this species have characteristic shape of epigyne and cannot be confused with the other two congeners occurring in the region; previously reported from the Northern Caucasus and Nakhchivan (Otto 2020).

Mesiotelus cf. *scopensis* Drensky, 1935

(Fig. 5)

Material examined: *Vayot Dzor Province:* 1♀, Gnishik River canyon, road to Noravank Monastery, 39°41'14"N 45°13'21"E, 1400 m, 10.v.2021. *Kotayk Province:* 2♀, env. of Solak, 40°28'24"N 44°42'57"E, 14.v.2021; 1♀, Vokhchabert, 40°09'56"N 44°38'59"E, 15.v.2021; 9♀, env. of Geghadir, 2 canyons nearby, 40°09'N 44°38'E, 15.v.2021.

Comments: The absence of males in our collected material does not allow us to identify this species with certainty. The epigyne of the Armenian specimens (Fig. 5D, E) is most similar to those illustrated for *M. scopensis*, but still differ in having straight and anteriorly diverging margins of the fovea (vs. converging and concave).

Fig. 5: Female of *Mesiotelus* cf. *scopensis*: (A) habitus, dorsal; (B) carapace, dorsal; (C) leg I, prolateral view showing numerous spines on patella and metatarsus; (D–E) epigyne of two different females, ventral. Scale = 0.2 mm, if not indicated otherwise.

The epigyne of our specimens is also similar to those of *M. lubricus* (Simon, 1880) known from Eastern China but differs in the straight epigynal margins (vs. rounded) and also in the presence of numerous small spines on tarsus I, lacking in *M. lubricus* (Fu *et al.* 2009: fig. 7). We have provided figures for habitus and leg I to illustrate the characteristic features of this species, representing a genus previously not reported in the Caucasus. *Mesiotelus scopensis* is known from the Balkans, westernmost Anatolia (Elverici *et al.* 2013; Nentwig *et al.* 2021). Record from Iran may refer to the same species as Armenian specimens.

Family Mimetidae Simon, 1881

Currently five species in three genera of this family are known in the Caucasus (Otto 2020) and none have been recorded from Armenia before.

Ero aphana (Walckenaer, 1802)

Material examined: *Vayots Dzor Province*: 1(♂), Shatin, Scenic place, 39°50'49"N 45°19'00"E, 9.v.2021.

Comments: Although the specimen is a subadult, it can be easily identified as this species due to the presence of four tubercles on the abdomen (vs. two or none in the other species). This species is the most common among all *Ero* species occurring in the Caucasus, and reported from 16 localities in Russia, Georgia and Azerbaijan (Otto 2020).

Ero furcata (Villers, 1789)

Material examined: *Kotayk Province*: 1♀, env. of Aghavnadzor, 40°33'56"N 44°40'43"E, 14.v.2021.

Comments: So far, this species was known only from the Northern Caucasus and northwestern Georgia (Otto 2020).

Mimetus laevigatus (Keyserling, 1863)

Material examined: *Ararat Province*: 1 juv., Garni Gorge, Azat River, 40°06'32"N 44°43'57"E, 1240 m, 17.v.2021; 1♀, env. of Goravan, Goravan Sands State Sanctuary, 39°53'51"N 44°43'35"E, 6.v.2021. *Vayots Dzor Province*: 1 juv., env. of Shatin, 39°51'44"N 45°20'19"E, meadow with lava stones, 9.v.2021. *Armavir Province*: 1♀, Jrarat, 40°04'59"N 44°11'26"E, collapsing clay cliffs and near water, 13.v.2021. *Kotayk Province*: 1(♂), env. of Geghadir, 2 canyons nearby, 40°09'N 44°38'E, 15.v.2021.

Comments: This is a single species of the genus in West Palaearctic and this is the commonest species of the family occurring in the Caucasus. It has been reported from 19 localities in Russia, Georgia and Azerbaijan (Otto 2020). In Armenia, it has been found in five localities.

Family Mysmenidae Petrunkevitch, 1928

So far, two species in the genera *Microdipoena* Banks, 1895 and *Mysmena* Simon, 1894 have been reported in the Caucasus (Mikhailov 2021). New to Armenia.

Fig. 6: Habitus of *Mysmena leucoplagiata*, female (A–B) and male (C–E): (A, C) dorsal; (B) latero-ventral; (D) ventral; (E) lateral. Scale = 0.2 mm.

Mysmena leucoplagiata (Simon, 1880)

(Fig. 6)

Material examined: *Ararat Province:* 1♂ Garni Gorge, Azat River, 40°06'32"N 44°43'57"E, 1240 m, 5.v.2021. *Vayot Dzor Province:* 1♀, Gnishik River canyon, road to Noravank Monastery, 39°41'14"N 45°13'21"E, 1400 m, 10.v.2021.

Comments: This species was previously known in the Caucasus and the entire former Soviet Union from a single locality in central-north Azerbaijan (Otto 2020). We have provided habitus figures to illustrate its characteristic pattern and features, which would aid identification of this species from the relatively similar *Microdipoena jobi* (Kraus, 1967): the epigyne with membranous, longer than wide scape and the cymbium with a conical extension furnished with curved setae (arrowed on Fig. 6D).

Family Oecobiidae Blackwall, 1862

Only the type genus (*Oecobius* Lucas, 1846) has been reported in the Caucasus, with five species known to occur in the region (Otto 2020) but none reported from Armenia.

Fig. 7: Habitus and epigyne of *Oecobius nadiae*: (A–B) males, dorsal; (C) female, dorsal; (D) epigyne, ventral. Scale = 0.2 mm, if not indicated otherwise.

Oecobius nadiae (Spassky, 1936)

(Fig. 7)

Material examined: *Ararat Province*: 1♂ 1 juv, Gami Gorge, Azat River, 40°06'32"N 44°43'57"E, 1240 m, 17.v.2021. *Yerevan*: 2♂ 1♀, city, on walls, 12–16.v.2021. *Vayot Dzor Province*: 2 juv., Gnishik River canyon, road to Noravank Monastery, 39°41'14"N 45°13'21"E, 1400 m, 10.v.2021.

Comments: In the Caucasus, this species was previously known only from four localities in Azerbaijan, including one in Nakhchivan (Otto 2020). The record from Armenia is northwesternmost in the entire range (from Armenia to Sichuan, China; WSC (2021)). We have provided figures of the male and female habitus that are lacking in the literature and in internet. Males have slightly variable abdominal pattern and may have distinct or indistinct leg annulations (cf. Figs 7A & 7B). The epigyne (Fig. 7D) of this species differs drastically from all congeners occurring in the Middle East.

Family Pholcidae C.L. Koch, 1850

Eight species in three genera are known to occur in the Caucasus (Otto 2020). Although some synanthropic species are widespread, none has been previously reported from Armenia. We have found at least four species belonging to three genera (*Holocnemus* Simon, 1873, *Pholcus* Walckenaer, 1805 and *Spermophora* Hentz, 1841); however, we are reporting only one of them that could have been identified to the species level with certainty. *Holocnemus* is a small genus (four species, three of which restricted to the West Mediterranean) previously reported from two republics of the former Soviet Union: Azerbaijan and Ukraine (Mikhailov 2021). For some reasons, these records are missing from Caucasian Spiders database (Otto 2020).

Holocnemus pluchei (Scopoli, 1763)

(Fig. 8)

Material examined: *Ararat Province:* 1♂, env. of Urtsadzor, 39°55'26"N 44°48'53"E, 1040 m, clay canyons, 6.v.2021. *Vayot Dzor Province:* 1♀ Gnishik River canyon, road to Noravank Monastery, 39°41'14"N 45°13'21"E, 1400 m, 10.v.2021. *Yerevan:* 2♂ 1 juv., suburb of Yerevan, Nubarashen, ca. 40°05'32"N 44°32'13"E, 1100 m, 12.v.2021; 2♀ 2 juv., city, indoors, v.2021.

Comments: *Holocnemus pluchei* is the only species of its genus with a wide distribution (almost cosmopolitan). Females and even juveniles of this species can be recognized due to their swollen palps (Fig. 8A–E). This species can be also recognized by the characteristic abdominal pattern, longitudinal spots on legs (Fig. 8C, D) and annulations (Fig. 8D). Furthermore, this species has a very deep and large thoracic fovea unknown in other pholcids occurring in the region (Fig. 8C, E).

Family Phrurolithidae Banks, 1892

Current version of the checklist of spiders occurring in the region lists only two species of *Phrurolithus* C.L. Koch, 1839, although there is one more genus (*Bosse-laerius* Zamani & Marusik, 2020) and two more species, namely *B. hyrcanicus* Zamani & Marusik, 2020 and *Phrurolithus azarkinae* Zamani & Marusik, 2020.

Phrurolithus azarkinae Zamani & Marusik, 2020

Phrurolithus azarkinae Zamani & Marusik, 2020b: 313, figs 1A–F, 2A–F, 3A–D (♂ ♀).

Material examined: *Ararat Province:* 3♂ 1♀ Garni Gorge, Azat River, 40°06'32"N 44°43'57"E, 1240 m, 5.v.2021; 3♀, env. of Urtsadzor, 39°54'00"N 44°50'53"E, 1200–1300 m, clay slope, 6.v.2021. *Vayots Dzor Province:* 3♂ 1 juv., Shatin, Scenic place, 39°50'49"N 45°19'00"E, 9.v.2021. *Armavir Province:* 2♂ 2♀ SW from Yerevan, Jrarbi, 40°04'46"N 44°14'27"E, saline ground and around water ponds, 13.v.2021 (YMM & V. Zh. Ambarzumyan). *Yerevan:* 1♂ 2♀ suburb of Yerevan, Nubarashen, ca. 40°05'32"N 44°32'13"E, 1100 m, 12.v.2021; 3♀, Botanical Garden, 40°12'38"N 44°33'25"E, sweeping & litter, 17.v.2021.

Comments: This recently described species was known from North-Central Azerbaijan east to Mazandaran and south to Fars Province in Iran (Zamani & Marusik 2020a, b). The current records extend the known range about 3° to the west.

Fig. 8: General appearance and epigyne of *Holcnemus pluchei*: (A, B) female, dorsal and ventral; (C, E) adult and subadult females, showing swollen palp and deep fovea; (D) female, lateral, showing characteristic leg pattern; (F) epigyne, ventral. Scale = 0.2 mm, if not indicated otherwise.

Phrurolithus festivus (C.L. Koch, 1835)

Material examined: Vayots Dzor Province: 3♂ 3♀, env. of Gnishik, 39°40'18"N 45°17'40"E, ca. 2030 m, 11.v.2021.

Comments: This is the most widespread species of the family in entire Holarctic (from Iberian Peninsula to Kuril Islands) (Mikhailov 2021; WSC 2021).

Family Sparassidae Bertkau, 1872

Two species of the family, *Olios sericeus* (Kroneberg, 1875) and *Micrommata virescens* (Clerck, 1757), have been previously reported in the Caucasus (Otto 2020; Mikhailov 2021).

Fig. 9: Habitus and copulatory organs of *Micrommata* cf. *ligurina*: (A, B) female and male habitus, dorsal; (C, D) male palp, ventral and retrolateral; (E) epigyne, ventral. Scale = 0.2 mm, if not indicated otherwise.

Micrommata cf. *ligurina* (C.L. Koch, 1845)

(Fig. 9)

Material examined: *Vayots Dzor Province*: 2♂, env. of Shatin, 39°51'44"N 45°20'19"E, meadow with lava stones, 9.v.2021; 2♂ ♀ 1 juv., Gnishik River canyon, road to Noravank Monastery, 39°41'14"N 45°13'21"E, 1400 m, 10.v.2021. *Kotayk Province*: 1♂ env. of Geghadir, 2 canyons nearby, 40°09'N 44°38'E, 15.v.2021

Comments: This identification is tentative, as these specimens may belong to an undescribed species, as *Micrommata ligurina* has not been recorded in the Caucasus. The females of *M. ligurina* differ from those of *M. virescens* in having a dark longitudinal spot on the carapace (Fig. 9A) (vs. lacking), and a longer epigynal septum (Fig. 9E). Males differ in different coloration of their appendages (light yellowish vs. green).

Olios ? *sericeus* (Kroneberg, 1875)

Material examined: *Yerevan*: 1(♀) suburb of Yerevan, Nubarashen, ca. 40°05'32"N 44°32'13"E, 1100 m, clay-stony cliff, 12.v.2021.

Comments: This identification is tentative, as we have only a single subadult female; other similar genera are not known in the region, and *O. sericeus* is the only species of the genus known to occur in the Caucasus, from two localities in Daghistan and Georgia (Otto 2020).

Family Uloboridae Thorell, 1869

This family is represented in the Caucasus by four species belonging to three genera (Otto 2020). None of these species were previously reported from Armenia.

Uloborus walckenaerius (Latreille, 1806)

Material examined: *Ararat Province:* 1♀, env. of Urtsadzor, 39°54'00"N 44°50'53"E, 1200–1300 m, on clay slope, 6.v.2021; 1♂, Garni Gorge, Azat River, 40°06'32"N 44°43'57"E, 1240 m, 5.v.2021; 2♀, env. of Goravan, Goravan Sands State Sanctuary, 39°53'51"N 44°43'35"E, 6.v.2021. *Armavir Province:* 1♀ SW from Yerevan, Jrarbi, 40°04'46"N 44°14'27"E, saline ground and around water ponds, 13.v.2021 & V.Zh. Ambardzumyan. *Yerevan:* 1 juv., Yerevan, Botanical Garden, 40°12'38"N 44°33'25"E, sweeping & litter, 17.v.2021.

Comments: This is the most widespread species of the genus both globally and regionally, 29 records in the Caucasus alone (Otto 2020).

CONCLUSIONS

This is the first paper in a series dealing with new findings of spider species in Armenia. During our joint collecting trip, several dozens of species and genera were collected, including species new to science. Besides the morphological approach, we are planning to involve molecular analyses and most of the material will be sent to the Caucasus Barcode of Life. Accounting the new findings, the total number of spider species reported from Armenia is raised to 219. Although this number is rather low, the share (22 %) of endemic (11 species) and subendemic species (known only in Armenia and adjacent countries, 11) is about the same as in the whole Caucasus (Marusik *et al.* 2006).

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